

Development of a Cable Dynamics Module for the Flow Solver CFDShip-Iowa

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Abstract—A cable dynamics module was developed and implemented in the Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes Equations (RANS) solver CFDShip-Iowa to model the dynamics of towed cable systems in high sea states and during the launch and recovery of tethered underwater vehicles from behind a ship. In previous cable dynamics simulations, the vehicle forces are computed using hydrodynamic coefficients which are only accurate for steady, uniform flows. For unsteady, energetic flows in sea states and/or in the ship turbulent wakes, this coefficient-based approach is inadequate, and high-fidelity RANS solution is needed to predict the unsteady fluid forces acting on the vehicles. The cable module is based on an existing cable program with modifications for integration in CFDShip-Iowa and additional capabilities including dynamics modeling of the towing vehicle. The cable itself is represented by a series of rigid cylinders or links connected end-to-end by spherical joints. Cable physical parameters and external forces are lumped at these joints, and all vehicles are treated as rigid bodies. This paper focuses on the theoretical development of the cable module and presents sample simulations of an underwater vehicle towing another vehicle in both calm water and in Sea State 3. More extensive simulations and validations will be included in a future paper.

Keywords—cable dynamics; RANS flow solver; vehicle motions in sea states.

I. INTRODUCTION

Dynamics cable modeling has a long history in mine sweeping and mine hunting. More recently, it is becoming important in Launch and Recovery (L&R) operations. Whether the towing vehicle is a helicopter, a surface ship or an underwater vehicle, capturing the nonlinear cable dynamics is essential to assessing the performance of the towed system. Up to now, the hydrodynamic forces acting on the vehicles in a cable system are modeled using a set of coefficients as shown in [1]. These coefficients are typically measured in a towing tank or wind tunnel but can also be estimated using semi-empirical codes such as Missile DATCOM and Aeroprediction 98 [2]. Hydrodynamic coefficients are the result of expanding forces and moments in terms of Taylor's series in small motion deviations about some equilibrium condition. Their use in maneuvering simulations in calm or uniform flows has become a standard practice due to their accuracy and efficiency. In recent years, hydrodynamic coefficients have also been applied to unsteady and non-uniform flow environments, but in view of

their Taylor's series origin, their accuracy may not be acceptable for some applications.

An accurate alternative, albeit more computationally expensive, to the coefficient-based approach is the use of Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes Equations (RANS) solver to compute the flow field and the forces and moments acting on the vehicles directly. Over the past several years, RANS flow solvers have reached a level of maturity at which computation of unsteady forces and moments on a wide range of vehicle geometries can be performed with an accuracy comparable to that achieved in towing tank or wind tunnel measurements. At the Naval Surface Warfare Center, Panama City Division (NSWC PCD), we have used the flow solver CFDShip-Iowa [3] extensively to compute the unsteady flows in ship wakes and around vehicles in high sea states. CFDShip-Iowa uses a level-set surface capturing algorithm to resolve the unsteady free-surface and a dynamic overset grid algorithm to allow a body to move in space while retaining consistent grid quality within a structured grid solver paradigm.

Given the importance of towed system analysis to the Navy, the logical step is to combine CFDShip-Iowa with a dynamics cable model to allow accurate towed system analysis in a highly unsteady flow environment. This paper presents the status and some preliminary results of this effort. In particular, it describes the development of a dynamics cable module and its integration in CFDShip-Iowa. Three example simulations are also given to illustrate the capabilities of the combined code. Additional simulations and extensive validations are currently being performed, and these results will be presented in a future paper.

The cable module described in this paper is based on the existing cable code DYNTOCABS (DYNamics of TOWed CABLE Systems) [4] developed at NSWC PCD. DYNTOCABS is written in FORTRAN 77 and uses a lumped parameter cable model for ease of handling complex branched cable systems. It also assumes the cable is towed from a large ship whose dynamics is unaffected by the cable tension. Ship motion is, therefore, a known variable and an input to the simulation but not part of the solution. In developing the cable module, it was soon realized that the modifications required are extensive enough that it is beneficial for future maintainability to rewrite the module completely in FORTRAN 90 to take advantage of its object-oriented programming features. Also, to

Figure 1. Coordinate systems and numbering conventions.

allow modeling of cable systems towed from small surface vessels or underwater vehicles, the dynamics of the towing vehicle is included in the formulation.

II. LUMPED PARAMETER CABLE MODEL

It is shown in [5] that for many towed cable systems, a lumped parameter model is adequate for simulating the cable dynamics while substantially increasing the execution speed. In this model, the cable is represented by a series of rigid cylinders or links connected end-to-end by frictionless spherical joints. The mass of each link is concentrated evenly at the two ends, and the cable can be visualized as a series of point masses connected by massless rods as shown in Fig. 1. The fluid and gravitational forces acting on each link are also divided evenly and concentrated at the end joints.

In this section, we derive the equations of motion for the links and the two vehicles. The equations for the towing and towed vehicles are essentially the same, but because of the link numbering convention described below, some of the terms will be different in sign. Fig. 1 shows the various coordinate systems used in the formulation. The earth-fixed system $Oxyz$ has the xy -plane coincident with the undisturbed free surface and the positive z -axis pointing downward. Its unit directional vectors i, j, k are along the x, y, z -axis, respectively. The vehicle-fixed frame $O'x'y'z'$ has the positive x' -axis pointing toward the vehicle nose and the positive z' -axis pointing downward. For ease of presentation, $I = 1$ indicates the towing vehicle and $I = 2$ the towed vehicle. The unit directional vectors for this frame are i', j', k' . The cable itself is modeled by N links where the links are numbered sequentially from 1 to N , as shown in Fig. 1, with link $K = 1$ attached to the towing vehicle. Similarly, the point masses are numbered from 0 to N with mass 0 located at the cable attachment point on the towing vehicle. The angular orientation of an arbitrary link K can be described by the two angles θ_1^K and θ_2^K as shown in Fig. 2. Angle θ_1^K is the

rotation angle about the y -axis, and angle θ_2^K is the rotation about the intermediate z' -axis. Since we assume the links are connected by frictionless joints, their torsional motions are, therefore, not modeled, and the rotational angle about the lengthwise axis is not needed.

A. Kinematics

With some of the notations defined, we can now begin our formulation by developing the relationships between the Cartesian and angular coordinates. Fig. 3 shows the unit vector p^K along an arbitrary link K directed from the lower numbered mass J to mass K . Using the following transformation matrix $[T^K]$ for the θ_1^K and θ_2^K rotations:

$$[T^K] = \begin{bmatrix} c_1^K c_2^K & -c_1^K s_2^K & s_1^K \\ s_2^K & c_2^K & 0 \\ -s_1^K c_2^K & s_1^K s_2^K & c_1^K \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where $c_i^K = \cos \theta_i^K$ and $s_i^K = \sin \theta_i^K$, we can express p^K as:

$$p^K = -c_1^K c_2^K i - s_2^K j + s_1^K c_2^K k \quad (2)$$

The relative velocity of K with respect to J is obtained by differentiating (2):

$$v^{K/J} = l^K \partial p^K / \partial t = l^K (p_{\theta_1}^K \dot{\theta}_1^K + p_{\theta_2}^K \dot{\theta}_2^K) \quad (3)$$

where l^K is the length of link K and

$$p_{\theta_1}^K = \partial p^K / \partial \theta_1 = s_1^K c_2^K i + c_1^K c_2^K k \quad (4)$$

$$p_{\theta_2}^K = \partial p^K / \partial \theta_2 = c_1^K s_2^K i - c_2^K j - s_1^K s_2^K k \quad (5)$$

Figure 2. Definition of link angles.

Figure 3. Cable link unit vector.

Note that the dot product of (4) and (5) yields:

$$\mathbf{p}_{\theta_1}^K \cdot \mathbf{p}_{\theta_2}^K = (c_1^K s_1^K c_2^K s_2^K - c_1^K s_1^K c_2^K s_2^K) = 0 \quad (6)$$

To obtain the time derivatives of the link angles $\dot{\theta}_i^K$, $i = 1, 2$, we dot multiply (3) by $\mathbf{p}_{\theta_i}^K$ and solve for $\dot{\theta}_i^K$, making use of the identity in (6):

$$\dot{\theta}_i^K = \mathbf{v}^{K/J} \cdot \mathbf{p}_{\theta_i}^K / (l^K |\mathbf{p}_{\theta_i}^K|^2), \quad i = 1, 2 \quad (7)$$

Similarly, for the second time derivatives of the link angles, we first differentiate (3) to yield the relative acceleration of K with respect to J :

$$\mathbf{a}^{K/J} = \partial \mathbf{v}^{K/J} / \partial t = \mathbf{p}_{\theta_1}^K \ddot{\theta}_1^K + \mathbf{p}_{\theta_2}^K \ddot{\theta}_2^K + \dot{\mathbf{p}}_{\theta_1}^K \dot{\theta}_1^K + \dot{\mathbf{p}}_{\theta_2}^K \dot{\theta}_2^K \quad (8)$$

The derivatives $\dot{\mathbf{p}}_{\theta_i}^K$ in (8) are obtained by differentiating (4) and (5) as follows:

$$\dot{\mathbf{p}}_{\theta_1}^K = (c_1^K c_2^K \dot{\theta}_1^K - s_1^K s_2^K \dot{\theta}_2^K) \mathbf{i} - (s_1^K c_2^K \dot{\theta}_1^K + c_1^K s_2^K \dot{\theta}_2^K) \mathbf{k} \quad (9)$$

$$\dot{\mathbf{p}}_{\theta_2}^K = (-s_1^K s_2^K \dot{\theta}_1^K + c_1^K c_2^K \dot{\theta}_2^K) \mathbf{i} + s_2^K \dot{\theta}_2^K \mathbf{j} - (c_1^K s_2^K \dot{\theta}_1^K + s_1^K c_2^K \dot{\theta}_2^K) \mathbf{k} \quad (10)$$

Finally, dot multiplying (8) by $\mathbf{p}_{\theta_i}^K$ and solving for $\ddot{\theta}_i^K$ yield:

$$\ddot{\theta}_i^K = (\mathbf{a}^{K/J} / l^K - \dot{\mathbf{p}}_{\theta_1}^K \dot{\theta}_1^K - \dot{\mathbf{p}}_{\theta_2}^K \dot{\theta}_2^K) \cdot \mathbf{p}_{\theta_i}^K / |\mathbf{p}_{\theta_i}^K|^2, \quad i = 1, 2 \quad (11)$$

Equations (7) and (11) allow us to compute the time derivatives of the link angles for numerical integration once we know the Cartesian accelerations of the point masses.

B. Equations of Motion

The equations of motion for the system are obtained by applying Newton's second law to each lumped mass in the cable and to each vehicle. The force vector \mathbf{f}^K acting on mass K consists of the internal cable tensions and the external components of weight, buoyant, and fluid drag forces. Drag force on the cable links can be computed in CFDShip-Iowa together with fluid forces on the vehicles. However, unlike vehicle forces, cable drag is well understood, and drag data for different cable types are usually available from the manufacturers. For efficiency, in our model, cable drag is computed using one of three commonly used methods: Reynolds-number-dependent drag coefficient, loading functions [4], or Morrison's equation [6]. By not solving for cable drag in CFDShip-Iowa, we eliminate the need for a high resolution mesh around the cable segment. In the lumped parameter model, the total external force \mathbf{q}^K on mass K is half the resultant of weight, buoyant, and drag forces acting on all adjacent cable links. The equation of motion for mass K not attached to a vehicle can then be written as:

$$m^K \mathbf{a}^K = t^L \mathbf{p}^L - t^K \mathbf{p}^K + \mathbf{q}^K \quad (12)$$

where m^K and \mathbf{a}^K are the mass and acceleration of mass K , and t^L and t^K are the cable tensions in link L and link K , respectively. For mass 0 attached to the towing vehicle as shown in Fig. 4, the equation of motion is:

$$m^0 \mathbf{a}^0 = t^l \mathbf{p}^l - \mathbf{T}^l + \mathbf{q}^0 \quad (13)$$

where \mathbf{T}^l is the internal force acting on the towing vehicle l by the cable. The internal force acting on mass 0 is equal and opposite and is $-\mathbf{T}^l$. Similarly, for mass N attached to the towed vehicle (see Fig. 5), its equation of motions is:

$$m^N \mathbf{a}^N = -t^N \mathbf{p}^N - \mathbf{T}^2 + \mathbf{q}^N \quad (14)$$

Figure 4. Towing vehicle and attached link and lumped mass.

Figure 5. Towed vehicle and attached link and lumped mass.

where \mathbf{T}^2 is the cable force acting on the towed vehicle 2.

The vehicles are modeled as rigid bodies with constant masses. With the exception of the cable force, the equations of motion are essentially the same as those for a free-swimming vehicle and can be found in many papers such as [7] and [8]. For brevity, we will not derive these equations here but simply introduce the variables involved and present the equations in their final form. These equations are commonly expressed in the body-fixed coordinate systems, as introduced earlier and shown in Fig. 1. In these systems, the cable force \mathbf{T}^I , $I = 1$ or 2, acting on vehicle I can be written as:

$$\mathbf{T}^I = T_1^I \mathbf{i}^I + T_2^I \mathbf{j}^I + T_3^I \mathbf{k}^I \quad (15)$$

Similarly, the velocity \mathbf{V}^I and acceleration \mathbf{A}^I of the origin O^I , the position vector \mathbf{r}_G^I of the center of mass, and the angular velocity $\boldsymbol{\omega}^I$ and acceleration $\boldsymbol{\alpha}^I$ are given by:

$$\mathbf{V}^I = u^I \mathbf{i}^I + v^I \mathbf{j}^I + w^I \mathbf{k}^I \quad (16)$$

$$\mathbf{A}^I = \dot{u}^I \mathbf{i}^I + \dot{v}^I \mathbf{j}^I + \dot{w}^I \mathbf{k}^I + \boldsymbol{\omega}^I \times \mathbf{V}^I \quad (17)$$

$$\mathbf{r}_G^I = x_G^I \mathbf{i}^I + y_G^I \mathbf{j}^I + z_G^I \mathbf{k}^I \quad (18)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\omega}^I = p^I \mathbf{i}^I + q^I \mathbf{j}^I + r^I \mathbf{k}^I \quad (19)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\alpha}^I = \dot{p}^I \mathbf{i}^I + \dot{q}^I \mathbf{j}^I + \dot{r}^I \mathbf{k}^I \quad (20)$$

The total external force \mathbf{f}^I and moment \mathbf{m}^I acting on the vehicle include the gravitational, buoyant and drag components and are computed in CFDShip-Iowa before they are passed to the cable module. If we denote the vehicle mass as m^I and the moment of inertia matrix as:

$$[\mathbf{I}^I] = \begin{bmatrix} I_{xx}^I & I_{xy}^I & I_{xz}^I \\ I_{xy}^I & I_{yy}^I & I_{yz}^I \\ I_{xz}^I & I_{yz}^I & I_{zz}^I \end{bmatrix} \quad (21)$$

then we can write the equations of motion in matrix form as:

$$[\mathbf{M}^I] \{\ddot{\mathbf{u}}^I\} = \{\mathbf{F}^I\} + \{\mathbf{T}^I\} \quad (22)$$

where the mass matrix $[\mathbf{M}^I]$ is:

$$\begin{bmatrix} m^I & 0 & 0 & 0 & m^I z_G^I & -m^I y_G^I \\ 0 & m^I & 0 & -m & 0 & m^I x_G^I \\ 0 & 0 & m^I & m^I y_G^I & -m^I x_G^I & 0 \\ 0 & -m^I z_G^I & m^I y_G^I & I_{xx}^I & I_{xy}^I & I_{xz}^I \\ m^I z_G^I & 0 & -m^I x_G^I & I_{xy}^I & I_{yy}^I & I_{yz}^I \\ -m^I y_G^I & m^I x_G^I & 0 & I_{xz}^I & I_{yz}^I & I_{zz}^I \end{bmatrix} \quad (23)$$

and the generalized acceleration vector is:

$$\{\ddot{\mathbf{u}}^I\}^T = \{\dot{u}, \dot{v}, \dot{w}, \dot{p}, \dot{q}, \dot{r}\}^T \quad (24)$$

The vector $\{\mathbf{F}^I\}^T = \{F_1^I, F_2^I, F_3^I, F_4^I, F_5^I, F_6^I\}^T$ contains the known velocities and external force and moment and is defined as follows:

$$F_1^I \mathbf{i}^I + F_2^I \mathbf{j}^I + F_3^I \mathbf{k}^I = \mathbf{f}^I - m^I [\boldsymbol{\omega}^I \times \mathbf{V}^I + \boldsymbol{\omega}^I \times (\boldsymbol{\omega}^I \times \mathbf{r}_G^I)] \quad (25)$$

$$F_4^I \mathbf{i}^I + F_5^I \mathbf{j}^I + F_6^I \mathbf{k}^I = \mathbf{m}^I - \boldsymbol{\omega}^I \times [\mathbf{I}^I] \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega}^I - m^I \mathbf{r}_G^I \times (\boldsymbol{\omega}^I \times \mathbf{V}^I) \quad (26)$$

The vector $\{\mathbf{T}^I\}^T = \{T_1^I, T_2^I, T_3^I, T_4^I, T_5^I, T_6^I\}^T$ is a function of the unknown cable force and is the additional term that does not exist in the equations of motion for a free-swimming vehicle. The first three elements of $\{\mathbf{T}^I\}$ are defined in (15), and the last three elements are given below:

$$T_4^I \mathbf{i}^I + T_5^I \mathbf{j}^I + T_6^I \mathbf{k}^I = \mathbf{r}^I \times \mathbf{T}^I \quad (27)$$

where $\mathbf{r}^I = x^I \mathbf{i}^I + y^I \mathbf{j}^I + z^I \mathbf{k}^I$ is the position vector from O^I to the cable attachment point of vehicle I .

C. Internal Cable Forces

The equations of motion (12) through (14) and (22) for the lumped masses and vehicles contain the unknown cable tensions t^K , $K = 1, N$ and \mathbf{T}^I , $I = 1, 2$. To compute these internal forces, we need to introduce additional equations imposing the rigidity condition on the cable links and the two vehicles. These constraint equations relate the positions, velocities, and accelerations of the adjacent lumped masses or adjacent lumped masses and vehicle coordinate origins. For a cable link, the rigidity condition can be represented mathematically by starting with the equation:

$$\mathbf{p}^K \cdot \mathbf{p}^K = 1 \quad (28)$$

Differentiating (27) twice with respect to time gives:

$$\mathbf{p}^K \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{p}}^K = -\dot{\mathbf{p}}^K \cdot \dot{\mathbf{p}}^K \quad (29)$$

If a link is rigid, $\dot{l}^K = 0$, and we have $\ddot{\mathbf{p}}^K = (\mathbf{a}^K - \mathbf{a}^J)/l^K$. Substituting this expression in (29), we obtain the constraint equation for the two adjacent end masses J and K as follows:

$$\mathbf{p}^K \cdot (\mathbf{a}^K - \mathbf{a}^J) = -l^K \dot{\mathbf{p}}^K \cdot \dot{\mathbf{p}}^K \quad (30)$$

Similarly, for the towing vehicle in Fig. 4, the constraint equation is:

$$-\mathbf{A}^l + \mathbf{a}^0 + \boldsymbol{\alpha}^l \times \mathbf{r}^l = -\boldsymbol{\omega}^l \times (\boldsymbol{\omega}^l \times \mathbf{r}^l) \quad (31)$$

and for the towed vehicle in Fig. 5, the equation is:

$$-\mathbf{A}^2 + \mathbf{a}^N + \boldsymbol{\alpha}^2 \times \mathbf{r}^2 = -\boldsymbol{\omega}^2 \times (\boldsymbol{\omega}^2 \times \mathbf{r}^2) \quad (32)$$

Substituting (12) through (14) and (22) into the constraint equations (30) through (32) results in a set of linear equations for the internal cable tensions. In the following, we present results for the general links, links attached to the vehicles, and results for the vehicles. For a general link K not attached to any vehicle, applying (12) to masses J and K and substituting the results in (30) yields:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu^J \mathbf{p}^J \cdot \mathbf{p}^{Kt^J} - (\mu^J + \mu^K)t^K + \mu^K \mathbf{p}^K \cdot \mathbf{p}^{Lt^L} = \\ \mathbf{p}^K \cdot (\mu^J \mathbf{q}^J - \mu^K \mathbf{q}^K) - l^K \dot{\mathbf{p}}^K \cdot \dot{\mathbf{p}}^K \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

where $\mu^K = 1/m^K$. For link l attached to the towing vehicle, substituting (12) for mass l and (13) for mass 0 into (30) gives:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu^J \mathbf{p}^K \cdot \mathbf{T}^l - (\mu^J + \mu^K)t^K + \mu^K \mathbf{p}^K \cdot \mathbf{p}^{Lt^L} = \\ \mathbf{p}^K \cdot (\mu^J \mathbf{q}^J - \mu^K \mathbf{q}^K) - l^K \dot{\mathbf{p}}^K \cdot \dot{\mathbf{p}}^K \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

For link N attached to the towed vehicle, substituting (12) for mass $N-1$ and (14) for mass N into (30) gives:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu^{N-1} \mathbf{p}^{N-1} \cdot \mathbf{p}^{Nt^{N-1}} - (\mu^{N-1} + \mu^N)t^N - \mu^N \mathbf{p}^N \cdot \mathbf{T}^2 = \\ \mathbf{p}^N \cdot (\mu^{N-1} \mathbf{q}^{N-1} - \mu^N \mathbf{q}^N) - l^N \dot{\mathbf{p}}^N \cdot \dot{\mathbf{p}}^N \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

The cable force equation for the towing vehicle is obtained by substituting (13), (17), (20), (22) into (31), and the equation for the towed vehicle is obtained by substituting (14), (17), (20), (22) into (32). The final form of these equations in terms of the introduced variables is rather cumbersome. To simplify, we define the following additional variables where, as before, the superscript $I = 1, 2$ indicating the towing and towed vehicle, respectively:

$$\hat{g}_1^I \mathbf{i}^I + \hat{g}_2^I \mathbf{j}^I + \hat{g}_3^I \mathbf{k}^I = -m^I [\boldsymbol{\omega}^I \times \mathbf{V}^I + \boldsymbol{\omega}^I \times (\boldsymbol{\omega}^I \times \mathbf{r}_G^I)] + \mathbf{f}^I \quad (36)$$

$$\hat{g}_4^I \mathbf{i}^I + \hat{g}_5^I \mathbf{j}^I + \hat{g}_6^I \mathbf{k}^I = -\boldsymbol{\omega}^I \times [I^I \boldsymbol{\omega}^I - m^I \mathbf{r}_G^I \times (\boldsymbol{\omega}^I \times \mathbf{V}^I)] + \mathbf{m}^I \quad (37)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \hat{g}_1^I \\ \hat{g}_2^I \\ \hat{g}_3^I \\ \hat{g}_4^I \\ \hat{g}_5^I \\ \hat{g}_6^I \end{Bmatrix} = [M^I]^{-1} \begin{Bmatrix} \hat{g}_1^I \\ \hat{g}_2^I \\ \hat{g}_3^I \\ \hat{g}_4^I \\ \hat{g}_5^I \\ \hat{g}_6^I \end{Bmatrix} \quad (38)$$

$$\mathbf{g}^I = g_1^I \mathbf{i}^I + g_2^I \mathbf{j}^I + g_3^I \mathbf{k}^I \quad (39)$$

$$\mathbf{h}^I = g_4^I \mathbf{i}^I + g_5^I \mathbf{j}^I + g_6^I \mathbf{k}^I \quad (40)$$

$$[\hat{D}^I] = [M^I]^{-1} \begin{Bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & -z^I & y^I \\ z^I & 0 & -x^I \\ -y^I & x^I & 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (41)$$

$$[D^I] = [\hat{D}^I(1:3,1:3)] \quad \text{and} \quad [E^I] = [\hat{D}^I(4:6,1:3)] \quad (42)$$

With these intermediate variables, the cable force equation for the towing vehicle is:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{p}^{lt^l} - \mathbf{T}^l - m^0 [D^I] \mathbf{T}^l - m^0 ([E^I] \mathbf{T}^l) \times \mathbf{r}^l = \\ -\mathbf{q}^0 + m^0 [\mathbf{g}^l + \boldsymbol{\omega}^l \times \mathbf{V}^l + \mathbf{h}^l \times \mathbf{r}^l + \boldsymbol{\omega}^l \times (\boldsymbol{\omega}^l \times \mathbf{r}^l)] \end{aligned} \quad (43)$$

and the equation for the towed vehicle is:

$$\begin{aligned} -\mathbf{p}^{Nt^N} - \mathbf{T}^2 - m^N [D^2] \mathbf{T}^2 - m^N ([E^2] \mathbf{T}^2) \times \mathbf{r}^2 = \\ -\mathbf{q}^N + m^N [\mathbf{g}^2 + \boldsymbol{\omega}^2 \times \mathbf{V}^2 + \mathbf{h}^2 \times \mathbf{r}^2 + \boldsymbol{\omega}^2 \times (\boldsymbol{\omega}^2 \times \mathbf{r}^2)] \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

D. Numerical Solution

In this section, the numerical solution of the system dynamics is described using the equations presented above. If the initial conditions of the system are known at some time \bar{t} , the motion of the system can be computed up to time $\bar{t} + d\bar{t}$ using the procedure given here. The time interval $d\bar{t}$ is governed by the flow solver CFDSHIP-IOWA, as described in the next section, and can be larger than the cable integration time step dt . It is assumed that the hydrodynamic forces \mathbf{f}^I and moments \mathbf{m}^I acting on the vehicles are known from CFDSHIP-IOWA and are constant within the interval $d\bar{t}$. The system initial conditions consist of the towing vehicle's translational and angular positions and velocities, the link angles and their first time derivatives, and the angular position and velocity of the towed vehicle. Using the system initial conditions and (2) through (5), the Cartesian positions and velocities of the lumped masses and towed vehicle can be computed. The external forces on the links and lumped masses are obtained next, and all these results can be used in (33)-(35) and (43), (44) to form a set of linear equations for the unknown cable tensions and forces. The matrix of the

linear equation is almost tri-diagonal, and the equations can be solved efficiently using Gaussian elimination and backward substitution. Once the cable tensions and forces are known, (12) through (14), (22) are used to obtain the Cartesian accelerations of the lumped masses and translational and angular accelerations of the vehicles. Finally, using (11), the second time derivatives of the link angles are computed, and numerical integration using fourth order Runge-Kutta method can be performed to advance the motion of the system to the next time step.

III. INTEGRATION OF CABLE MODULE IN CFDSHIP-IOWA

Integration of the cable module into CFDSHIP-Iowa is accomplished by replacing the vehicle 6DOF solver in CFDSHIP-Iowa with the cable module which includes both a 6DOF time integrator and a cable dynamics solver. CFDSHIP-Iowa is written in FORTRAN 90 for parallel implementation while the cable module is written for serial use. Therefore, one processor is reserved for cable calculations and information communicated to other processors as needed. Fig. 6 is a flow chart showing how the cable module is inserted into the flow solver. Additional details of CFDSHIP-Iowa can be found in [3].

Figure 6. Flowchart – integration of cable module into CFDSHIP-Iowa.

Figure 7. Towing in calm water with heavy cable.

The integrated code was used for several towing conditions of which only two are described here due to length limitation. The chosen cases illustrate the range of system parameters that can be simulated by the integrated code. The first case is a buoyant vehicle towing another buoyant vehicle using a heavy cable in calm sea. The second case uses the same vehicles, but the cable is buoyant and the sea is a State 3. This case is representative of a launch and recovery operation at sea. In both cases the towing and towed vehicles are geometrically the same, but the towing vehicle is constrained in each of the rotational directions and is given an artificially high inertia. In both cases, simulation starts with the system at rest. The towing vehicle uses a propeller momentum disc model to accelerate while the towed vehicle is not self-propelled.

Results of the simulation are shown in Fig. 7 and 8. The heavier-than-water cable in case 1 produces a cable catenary which causes the towed vehicle to pitch down and be pulled under water due to the weight of the cable. The buoyant cable in case 2 is floating and is not always taut. Both vehicles are responding to the sea state, and this coupled with the slack

Figure 8. Towing in Sea State 3 with buoyant cable.

cable causes a snap of the cable and a jerk on the towed vehicle during the simulation. Both simulations produce reasonable results. Verification and comparison with experimental data published in the open literature will be presented in a future paper.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

A cable dynamics module was developed and implemented in the flow solver CFDShip-Iowa to allow simulations of cable systems in high sea states or in energetic flow environments such as ship wakes. The latter is normally encountered during launch and recovery operations. The cable module is based on the existing cable code DYNTOCABS which uses a lumped parameter model of the cable for efficiency. Capability of modeling the towing vehicle dynamics is added to enable better assessment of the towed system stability. Also included is the option of using different integration time steps for the cable dynamics and the flow solver. This option increases the robustness of the computation since the cable can undergo highly nonlinear motions and small time step is sometimes necessary for numerical convergence. Two sample simulations of an underwater vehicle towing another vehicle in calm sea and in Sea State 3 are presented in the paper. Additional simulations and validations with existing experimental data will be included in a future paper.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. A. Abkowitz, *Stability and Motion Control of Ocean Vehicles*. Cambridge, MA: The M.I.T. Press, 1969.
- [2] T. J. Sooy and R. Z. Schmidt, "Aerodynamic predictions, comparisons, and validation using Missile DATCOM (97) and Aeroprediction 98 (AP98)," *J. of Spacecraft and Rockets*, vol. 42, pp. 257-265, 2005.
- [3] P. M. Carrica, R. V. Wilson, and F. Stern, "An unsteady single-phase level set method for viscous free surface flows," *Int. J. for Num. Meth. in Fluid*, vol. 53, pp. 229-256, 2006.
- [4] J. W. Kamman, T. C. Nguyen, and J. W. Crane, "Modeling towed cable systems dynamics," OCEANS 89 Conference, Seattle, Washington, September 1989.
- [5] H. Wilson and L. C. Wang, "Computational methods for 3D dynamics of cables," BER Report No. 414-58, Bureau of Engineering Research, University of Alabama, 1987.
- [6] T. Sarpkaya, *Wave Forces on Offshore Structures*. New York, NY: Cambridge University Press, 2010.
- [7] P. H. Zipfel, "Modeling and simulation of aerospace vehicle dynamics," 2nd edition, AIAA Education Series, 2007.
- [8] D. T. Greenwood, *Principles of Dynamics*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall, Inc, 1988.